

TRIPS Agreement and Intellectual Property Rights Protection: Some Issues

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Received : 11/02/2021

1st BPR : 17/02/2021

2nd BPR : 23/02/2021

Accepted : 11/03/2021

Abstract

In today's world, ideas and knowledge have become a progressively important part of world trade. A creative mind is a scarce commodity, to be found only infrequently. Inventions, innovations, high technology products and processes, and medicines have intellectual origin and high commercial value, so do works of literature and arts. Their inventors and creators deserve to be compensated for the creative value inherent in these products, processes and creations. They are the intellectual property or assets of the inventors and creators. Logically, ethically and morally, they deserve to have a right to negotiate the commercial value of their intellectual assets. In a globalizing world economy, with brisk expansion of trade, FDI and technology transfer, there was a rapid growth in the commercial exploitation of the intellectual assets. The international law in the area of IPRs, was fairly underdeveloped and was unable to serve the rapidly integrating global economy in an efficacious manner. Hence a pressing need for systematic improvement was felt by both the developing and the industrial country.

Keywords: WTO, TRIPS, Intellectual Property.

Introduction

IPR deals with the ideas and expressions that are the products of human intellect. By providing a status of property, the originators of these ideas and expressions enjoy the status of an owner as in the case of other kind of property. Subject to exceptions and limitations, IPR provide exclusive rights to exploit his creations and innovations. For instance, law of Copy rights entitles authors of literary and artistic works with a variety of rights which depends upon the nature of the work. Similarly, trademarks law entitles the proprietor to use the mark in relation to goods. Patents Act allows the patentee to exercise his rights in relations to his inventions. Designs Act permits the design owner to enjoy exclusive rights in relation to appearance of a product. Similarly, the Geographical indications Act confer exclusive rights to the producers or the authorized users to use a particular mark in relation to goods in respect of which the GI is registered.

IPRs allow its holder a right to exclude others from certain business opportunities. IPRs though presented as exclusive rights, are in fact a monopoly of sorts. Stated differently IPRs are incorporation of wealth and property.

The economic and trade policies of independent nations with regard to goods or services, have acquired international dimensions. At the same time illegal trade in products which enjoyed intellectual property protection, has developed as an off-shoot. This trade which is generally known as piracy (unauthorized reproduction for commercial purposes) is growing at an alarming rate and causing a loss of billions of dollars to the nations around the world including India. Adoption of intensive rules and regulations to check illegal practice was felt to be a priority step to protect not only lawful owner but also of the government that suffers revenue loss due to tax evasion.

The customer's interest is also at jeopardy as he is often deceived and dissatisfied due to the counterfeit products. IP laws especially, Copy rights and trademarks entitle the IPR owner to take both civil and penal actions against the unscrupulous persons involved in the illegal trade. Legal remedies for enforcement of rights in a court of law no doubt are appropriate way of protecting IPR owners but in case of international trade where goods cross the national boundaries, the very prevention of infringing goods from entering the national territories or confiscation of such goods may be considered as an effective remedy. Though administrative in nature, the remedy proved to be effective in arresting dissemination of infringing goods into commercial channels of the state.

Origin of TRIPS Agreement

The Uruguay Round (1986-1994) is a watershed in this regard. Before the launch of the Uruguay round, there was no specific agreement on IPRs within the framework of the multilateral trading system. IPRs were regarded as the domain of the specialist organizations, treaties and conventions in this area. The multilateral negotiations during the Uruguay Round altered this status by incorporating IPRs into the multilateral trading system. The Trade- Related Aspects of Intellectual Property (TRIPS) Agreement was negotiated during the Uruguay Round and came into force on 1st Jan 1995, introducing IPRs into the multilateral trading system for the first time. Conclusion of the TRIPS Agreement was a noteworthy achievement. It is a key agreement of the WTO, widely regarded as a significant institutional improvement. It sets down minimum standards for many forms of intellectual property regulation. It is a key agreement of the WTO and is often described as one of the three pillars of the WTO. The other two pillars are trade in goods and trade in services.

Infact the TRIPS Agreement has not appeared out of a vacuum. It is the culmination of a long maturation of which the root goes a long way back, notably to the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) of 1947, the Berne Convention for protection of Literary and Artistic works of 1886 and the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property of 1883. It took a very long time for its seeds to grow and came into existence in 1995.

The Main Features of the TRIPS Agreement

The agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Right (the “TRIPS Agreement”) is contained in Annex 1C of the Marrakesh Agreement Establishing the world Trade Organization (the “WTO Agreement”) of 15 April 1994. The Agreement aims to ensure the adequate protection and effective enforcement of intellectual property right and the impartial resolution of disputes between WTO members about such matters, to the mutual advantage of both producers and users of intellectual property.

The areas of intellectual property that the TRIPS Agreement covers are: copyright and related rights (i.e. the right of performers, producers of sound recordings and broadcasting organizations); trademarks including service marks; geographical indications; industrial designs; patents, including the protection of new varieties of plants; the layout-designs of integrated circuits; and undisclosed information, including trade secrets and test data. In respect of each of these areas of intellectual property, the Agreement sets out the minimum standards of protection to be provided by each member. Each of the main elements of protection is defined, namely the subject matter to be protected, the rights to be conferred and permissible exceptions to those right, and the minimum duration of protection. The standards build on those in the main pre existing WIPO Conventions, substantive provisions of which are incorporated into the Agreement by reference.

The second main set provisions in the Agreement lays down requirements for national procedures and remedies for the enforcement of intellectual property right (IPRs): general principles applicable to all IPR enforcement procedures; civil and administrative procedures and remedies; provisional measures; special border enforcement measures; and criminal procedures. These procedures and remedies must enable right holders to enforce their rights effectively and also provide for safeguards against the abuse of procedures and remedies as barriers to legitimate trade.

The Agreement makes disputes between WTO members about the respect of TRIPS obligations subject to the WTO’s integrated dispute settlement procedures. In addition the Agreement provides for certain basic principles, such as national and most-favoured-nation treatment, and some general rules to ensure that procedural difficulties in acquiring or maintaining IPR do not nullify the substantive benefits that should flow from the Agreement.

The TRIPS Agreement is an integral part of the WTO Agreement, and it is binding on each member of the WTO from the date the WTO Agreement becomes effective for it. However, the TRIPS Agreement gives members transitional periods, which differ according to their stage of development, to bring themselves into compliance with its rules. The Agreement is administered by the Council for TRIPS, open to all members, which reports to the WTO General Council.

As in other WTO agreement and the WTO Agreement itself, the TRIPS Agreement contains a detailed Preamble where the negotiating parties expressed the objectives that they sought in adopting this component of the WTO system. While the provisions of the Preamble reflect, to some extent, the different positions that the negotiating parties brought to the negotiating table, they substantially respond to the protectionist paradigm advocated by the United States and other developed countries with regard to intellectual property.

“Members, desiring to reduce distortions and impediments to international trade, and taking into account the need to promote effective and adequate protection of intellectual property rights and to ensure that measures and procedures to enforce intellectual property rights do not themselves become barriers to legitimate trade.”

Objectives of TRIPS Agreement

One of the objectives of WTO/TRIPS was to eliminate or minimize the hurdles that prove to be barriers for legitimate trade among the member countries with increase in the volume of international trade in goods and services. Protection of right of owners of goods including IPR posed a great challenge before the international community. Meager provision on the enforcement of IPR under the Berne and Paris conventions, weak or absence of protection in many developing countries and abnormal increase in the incidence of piracy and trade in goods with counterfeit trademarks forced the industries of developed countries, especially US, England and Japan to bring IPR within the GATT regime. These countries had a view that uniform protection of IPR including the protection of substantive rights and rules of procedure for enforcement of rights would not only ensure an effective and efficient international protection in all countries but would also facilitate foreign direct investment and technology transfer. Much to the expectations of these countries WTO/GATT in 1994 included TRIPS Agreement to deal with IPR. The entire member countries are obliged to adopt various civil, penal and administrative measures to enforce IPR both within its territorial jurisdiction and at the border where goods imported have to cross the national frontier for trade. Special measure known as border measure require the contracting States to include elaborate provision for arresting the dissemination of goods at the entry point so that such goods does not enter into the main channels of commerce and cause irreparable loss to the interest of the true owner and pose danger for paralyzing the national economy.

Seeking The Right Balance

An objective of intellectual property protection is to promote long term public interest by means of providing exclusive rights to right holders for a limited duration of time. After the expiration of the term of protection, protected works and inventions fall into the public domain and anyone is free to use them without prior authorization by the right holder. Hence, in the long term there is no conflict but rather a mutually supportive relation between the interests of promoting creativity and innovation and maximizing access. However, during the course of the term of protection, there is potential for conflict between these two considerations, which can also mirror differences between the interests of right holder and users. The challenge of the national and international rule-makers is to find the optimal balance between various competing interests with a view to maximizing the public good, while meeting also the human rights of authors and inventors, Article 7 of the TRIPS Agreement emphasizes the need for balance: “the mutual advantage of producers and users of technological knowledge” and “a balance of rights and obligations”.

An optimal balance within IP systems at the national or multilateral level can be reached by properly determining the definition of protectable subject matter, scope of rights, permissible limitations and term of protection. This balance is constantly developing both at the national and international level in response to economic and technological as well as political developments. The TRIPS Agreement is a minimum rights agreement that leaves a fair amount of leeway to member countries to implement its provisions within their own legal system and practice and fine-tune the balance in the light of domestic public policy considerations. An important part of the balance is a careful definition of protectable subject matter. For example, copyright protection does not cover any information or ideas contained in a work: it only protects the original way that such information or ideas have been expressed in a work. As regards patents, the starting-point in the TRIPS Agreement is that for an invention to be patentable it must be new, involve an inventive step and be capable of industrial application. For example, biological material in its natural state is not patentable. Furthermore, the Agreement recognizes the importance of ethical and other considerations by allowing a country, even where an invention meets the normal rules for patentability, to refuse to grant a patent if the commercial exploitation of the invention is prohibited on grounds of public order or morality, including if its exploitation might be dangerous to life or health or seriously prejudicial to the environment. Diagnostic, therapeutic and surgical methods for the treatment of humans or animals are excluded from patentability. In addition, the TRIPS Agreement provides for some special flexibility in the area of biotechnology, allowing members to refuse patents for plant and animal inventions (other than microorganisms and microbiological processes).

One of the basic objectives of the patent system is to facilitate the dissemination of technological knowledge by encouraging inventors to disclose new technology rather than attempt to keep it secret. Article 29.1 of the

Agreement requires that an applicant for a patent shall disclose the invention in a manner sufficiently clear and complete for the invention to be carried out by others. The resulting information, which is stored and classified in patent documentation, is accessible to anyone, including to those in countries where a patent has not been sought. One of the purposes of this disclosure requirement together with the research or experimental use exception that is typically found in national patent laws is to ensure that the technological and scientific knowledge contained in a patented invention can be used for further research already during the patent term.

Copyright protection does not cover any information or ideas contained in a work; it only protects the original way that such information or ideas have been expressed in a work. Thus everyone is free to use the information contained in a work. In addition, the TRIPS Agreement and national copyright laws contain numerous specific limitations that allow free use of a work, including in regard, inter alia, to circulation of news and education. An Appendix to the Berne Convention, also incorporated into the TRIPs Agreement, allows developing countries, under certain conditions, to grant compulsory licenses for educational purposes.

The preoccupation in the TRIPS Agreement with balance is also reflected in the provisions concerning enforcement of intellectual property rights. While the Agreement requires that enforcement procedures must be such as to permit effective action, it also requires that they must be applied in a manner that avoids the creation of barriers to legitimate trade and safeguards against their abuse must be provided. Such procedures must be fair and equitable.

The Border Measures

As per Article 51 of TRIPs Agreement, member countries shall adopt rules as provided hereunder to enable a right holder, who has valid grounds for suspecting that the importation of goods, with counterfeit trademarks, or pirated copyright goods may take place, to lodge an application for the suspension by the custom authorities of the free circulation of goods. Briefly other rules that are framed under Article 57 to 60 of TRIPS are –

(i) Adequate evidence and identification of goods

As per Article 52, the rights holder desirous of initiating the procedure under Article 51 is required to provide adequate evidence to satisfy the customs authorities that there is prima-facie an infringement of his copyright. He shall also supply a sufficiently detailed description of goods, to make them readily recognizable by the customs authorities. The competent authorities shall inform the applicant within a reasonable period whether they have accepted the application and where determined by the competent authorities, the period for which the customs authorities will take action.

(ii) Security or assurance to prevent abuse

As per Article 53, the customs authorities shall have power to require an applicant to provide a security or equivalent assurance sufficient to protect the defendant and the competent authorities and to prevent abuse. However, such security or assurance shall not be of such a kind that it would unreasonably deter recourse to these procedures. While under Article 54, the importer and the applicant shall be promptly notified by the customs authorities.

(iii) Duration of suspension

Under Article 55 if within ten working days after the service of notice by the customs authorities, the applicant has not informed the custom authorities that proceedings leading to a decision on the merits of the case have been initiated (Particularly where this has to be done in a court and not before the same customs authorities) then the goods suspended shall be released. In other cases, the importer will have an opportunity, within a reasonable period of time, of being heard and of requesting a revocation or modification of the order.

(iv) Compensation for wrongful detention

Under Article 56, the customs authorities shall have a power to order the applicant to pay the importer, the consignee and the owner of the goods appropriate compensation for any injury caused to them through the wrongful detention of goods.

(v) Inspection of Goods

Under Article 57, the rights holder is to be given sufficient opportunity to inspect the goods detained by the custom authorities in order to substantiate his claim. The authorities shall also have the power to give the importer an equivalent opportunity to have such goods inspected. Where a positive determination is made on the merits of a case, the competent authorities shall have the power to inform the right holder of the names and addresses of the consigner, the importer and the consignee and the quality of goods in question.

(vi) 'Suo motu' initiatives

Under Article 58, member countries may include optional provision where the customs authorities may act upon their own initiative, without an application being required from the right holder and suspend the clearance of goods in respect of which they have acquired a prima facie evidence that IPR is being violated.

(vii) Remedies

Under Article 59, competent authorities i.e., the custom department or the Court should be empowered to dispose of or destroy the infringing goods, so that they do not enter into the channels of commerce. With regard to counterfeit trademarks in goods, the authorities shall not allow re-exportation of infringing goods in an unaltered state, or subject them to a different customs procedure, other than in exceptional circumstances. These remedies are without prejudice to other rights of action open to the right holder, such as to obtain damages through civil litigation, and are also subject to the right of the defendant to seek review by judicial authority.

(viii) 'De Minimis' imports

Under article 60, small quantities of infringing goods of non commercial nature contained in the personal baggage or sent in small consignments may be exempted from the purview of these border measures.

Conclusion

The protection and enforcement of intellectual property rights should contribute to the promotion of technological innovation and to the transfer and dissemination of technology, to the mutual advantage of producers and users of technological knowledge and in a manner conducive to social and economic welfare, and to a balance of rights and obligations. Hence when protection and enforcement of IPRs are guaranteed, the promotion of technological innovation might follow; then, the transfer and dissemination of technology will occur. At last, there will be mutual advantages for both producers and users of technological knowledge. The right owners will be paid for their contribution to the advancement of the standard of living and to the enjoyment of economic and social rights; and the whole society, experiencing the social and economic welfare, will be the ultimate beneficiary of the scientific and technological progress.

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